

Designation	Damage rating ^a	Reaction
ARC11324	6.3	S
Bahbolon	5.0	MR
B4032D-MR-1-3-1	6.5	S
CI 5662-2	6.8	S
Citanduy	3.9	MR
GH147 (M) KRAD-78	5.0	MR
GH147 (M) 30KRAD-C-PN7	6.5	S
GH147 (M) 40KRAD 89	7.4	S
IR13240-82-2-3-2-3-1	6.6	S
IR13475-7-3-2	3.7	MR
IR13458-117-2-3-2-3	5.2	MR
IR15529-253-3-2-2-2	4.1	MR
IR15529-256-1	4.3	MR
IR15795-151-2-3-2-2	4.8	MR
IR17307-11-2-3-2	6.7	S
IR2035-117-3	5.3	MR
IR18350-93-2	7.7	S
IR21820-154-3-2-2-3	6.1	S
IR25586-108-1-2-2-2	6.2	S
IR27325-27-3-3	4.2	MR
IR13475-7-3-2	5.1	MR
IR28154-101-3-2	2.4	R
IR29692-65-2-3	5.4	MR
IR31803-32-2	7.6	S
IR32307-107-3-22	3.3	R
IR32429-47-3-2-2	5.3	MR
IR2035-117-3	4.9	MR
IR60	5.0	MR
IR64 (IR18348-36-3-3)	3.2	R
Palman 46	5.8	S
Rathu Heenati	1.7	R
ARC6248 (resistant check)	1.9	R
TN1 (susceptible check)	8.9	S

^a Means of 40 plants.

after infestation. Individual plant damage was scored using the *Standard evaluation system for rice*. Mean reaction of all plants was used to classify an accession as resistant (R, 0-3.49), moderately resistant (MR, 3.5-5.49), or susceptible (S, 5.5-9).

Four accessions scored R, 15 MR, and 12 S (see table). IR2035-117-3, which is homozygous for *Wbph 1* and *Wbph 2* and is being used as a R check at IRR1, was MR in our tests, indicating a difference in biotype at IRR1 and at PAU. Earlier, we reported that *Wbph 1* and *Wbph 2* are not effective in conferring resistance to WBPH in Punjab. □

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Genetic Evaluation and Utilization OTHER PESTS

Yield ability of rice varieties in fields infested with root-knot nematode

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We measured yields of three Thai rice varieties — RD6, Khao Dawk Mali 105, and Hahng Yi 71 — growing in fields infested with root-knot nematode

Meloidogyne graminicola Golden and Birchfield in an experiment at Ubonratchathani Rice Research Center in 1986. The varieties have been considered resistant, moderately resistant, and susceptible.

The experiment, in 4 replications, was under upland conditions in 5- × 7-m plots with 25- × 25-cm spacing. Plots

Yield of rice varieties grown in fields infested with root-knot nematode *M. graminicola*. Ubonratchathani Rice Research Center, Thailand, 1986.

Variety	Yield ^a (t/ha)		Loss (%)
	Non-treated	Treated	
RD6	3.8	4.3	11.6
Khao Dawk Mali 105	3.6	4.4	18.2
Hahng Yi 71	2.9	4.3	32.6

^aAv of 4 replications.

were fertilized with 24-24-12 kg NPK/ ha. In control plots, we applied 60 kg carbofuran 3 G/ ha; no nematocide was applied in test plots.

Yield loss was highest with Hahng Yi 71 (see table). □

Genetic Evaluation and Utilization ADVERSE SOILS TOLERANCE

Tiller growth as an index of salinity resistance

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Tiller growth as an index of salinity resistance was evaluated. Seeds of resistant and sensitive cultivars were

Effect of NaCl on the tiller growth of rice cultivars, Baroda, India.

Cultivar	Salinity index ^a	Tillers (no./plant)	Decrease (%) from control in		
			Tiller height	Fresh weight of tillers/plant	Dry weight of tillers/plant
<i>Salt-resistant</i>					
Co 43	58.8	39	14	46	50
CSC1	50.9	46	12	41	29
AU1	45.6	20	14	27	15
<i>Salt-sensitive</i>					
GR3	42.2	50	46	75	84
TKM9	23.5	35	21	46	51
Co 36	21.1	64	43	85	94
IR20	13.6	83	73	93	93
CSC2	5.2	46	7	33	34
TKM4	0.9	85	78	94	97
Mean	30.2	52	34	60	61

^aSalinity index = $\frac{\text{grain yield of treated plants}}{\text{grain yield of control}} \times 100$.